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**PREVALENCE OF DEMENTIA AMONG
THE PATIENTS PRESENTING IN
OUTDOOR DEPARTMENT**

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ABSTRACT:
Dementia occurs as a set of related symptoms when the brain is damaged by disease. The symptoms involve progressive impairments to memory, thinking, and behavior, that affect the ability to perform everyday activities. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, and symptoms of dementia were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 80 patients presenting in the emergency department were included in this study i.e., 40 males (50%) and 40 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 45.12±4.12 years. Out of these patients, three patients had the symptoms of dementia. Further management was planned accordingly.

Keyword: Dementia

INTRODUCTION:

Dementia occurs as a set of related symptoms when the brain is damaged by disease. The symptoms involve progressive impairments to memory, thinking, and behavior, that affect the ability to perform everyday activities. Other common symptoms include emotional problems, difficulties with language, and decreased motivation. Dementia is not a disorder of consciousness, and consciousness is not usually affected. A diagnosis of dementia requires a change from a person's usual mental functioning, and a greater cognitive decline than that due to normal aging. Several diseases, and injuries to the brain such as a stroke can give rise to dementia which all have a significant effect on relationships and caregivers. In DSM-5, dementia has been reclassified as a major neurocognitive disorder, with varying degrees of severity, and many causative subtypes.

Causative subtypes of dementia may be based on a known potential cause such as Parkinson's disease, for Parkinson's disease dementia; Huntington's disease for Huntingtons disease dementia; vascular disease for vascular dementia; brain injury including stroke often results in vascular dementia; or many other medical conditions including HIV infection for HIV dementia; and prion diseases. Subtypes may be based on various symptoms as may be due to a neurodegenerative disorder such as Alzheimer's disease; frontotemporal lobar degeneration for frontotemporal dementia; or Lewy body disease for dementia with Lewy bodies. More than one type of dementia, known as mixed dementia, may exist together. Diagnosis is usually based on history of the illness and cognitive testing with imaging, and blood tests to rule out other possible causes, and to determine the particular subtype. The mini mental state examination is one commonly used cognitive test. The greatest risk factor for developing dementia is aging, however dementia is not a normal part of aging. Several risk factors for dementia are described with some such as smoking, and obesity being preventable by lifestyle changes. Screening the general population for the disorder is not recommended (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, and symptoms of dementia were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 80 patients presenting in the emergency department were included in this study i.e., 40 males (50%) and 40 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 45.12 ± 4.12 years. Out of these patients, three patients had the symptoms of dementia. Further management was planned accordingly.

DISCUSSION:

Symptoms are similar across dementia types and it is difficult to diagnose by symptoms alone. Diagnosis may be aided by brain scanning techniques. In many cases, the diagnosis requires a brain biopsy to become final, but this is rarely recommended (though it can be performed at autopsy). In those who are getting older, general screening for cognitive impairment using cognitive testing or early diagnosis of dementia has not been shown to improve outcomes. However, screening exams are useful in 65+ persons with memory complaints. Normally, symptoms must be present for at least six months to support a diagnosis. Cognitive dysfunction of shorter duration is called delirium. Delirium can be easily confused with dementia due to similar symptoms. Delirium is characterized by a sudden onset, fluctuating course, a short duration (often lasting from hours to weeks), and is primarily related to a somatic (or medical) disturbance. In comparison, dementia has typically a long, slow onset (except in the cases of a stroke or trauma), slow decline of mental functioning, as well as a longer trajectory (from months to years).

Some mental illnesses, including depression and psychosis, may produce symptoms that must be differentiated from both delirium and dementia. Therefore, any dementia evaluation should include a depression screening such as the Neuropsychiatric Inventory or the Geriatric Depression Scale. Physicians used to think that people with memory complaints had depression and not dementia (because they thought that those with dementia are generally unaware of their memory problems). This is called pseudodementia. However, in recent years researchers have realized that many older people with memory complaints in fact have MCI, the earliest stage of dementia. Depression should always remain high on the list of possibilities, however, for an elderly person with memory trouble. Changes in thinking, hearing and vision are associated with normal ageing and can cause problems when diagnosing dementia due to the similarities (4-6).

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